

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND PERFORMANCE OF MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS IN ETHIOPIA

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Abstract

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) are organizations that provide financial services to low-income individuals and communities. Corporate governance refers to the systems, processes, and principles by which an organization is directed and controlled. In the microfinance sector, effective corporate governance is crucial because donors, investors, and other funding providers need assurances that the funds provided will be used effectively and in alignment with the mission of MFIs. This article aims to study the impact of corporate governance characteristics on MFIs financial and social performance between (2015- 2022). ROA is used as the measure of financial performance and outreach indicated by number of credit clients served--for social performance. The empirical analysis is based on primary collected from individual MFIs and secondary data. obtained from the National Bank of Ethiopia and AEMFI. A random effects regression model was used to assess the effect of corporate governance mechanisms on MFIs' financial and social performance.

The results show that board size, the educational qualification of the members of boards and financial experience have a positive and significant impact on financial performance. However, board size and financial experience have a negative and significant relationship with social performance, indicating a possible conflict between the financial sustainability of impact enterprises and their outreach goals. Board gender diversity has a positive

statistically significant effect on the scope of corporate social outreach but no such effect on financial performance. Likewise, board meetings positively affect social performance while having no effects on financial performance. The findings also show that the educational qualifications of board members do better in improving financial performance, but not in social outreach. Furthermore, there is no significant relationship between financial and social performance with audit committee size. The study concludes that corporate governance plays an important role in shaping the dual mission of MFIs; therefore, MFIs and regulators should promote balanced board composition, gender diversity, regular board meetings, and a mix of financial and social expertise to strengthen both financial sustainability and social outreach.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, financial performance, Social Performance, Microfinance institution, Ethiopia.

I. Introduction

Microfinance is defined as the supply of financial services (mainly savings and credit) to the poor and low-income households that do not have access to the traditional commercial banking facilities (Rock et al., 1998). Most microfinance institutions (MFIs) have two goals, unlike the formal financial institutions, to intensify coverage of poor clients (social performance) and remain financially sustainable by meeting the operational expenses (Hermes & Lensink, 2011). In this notion, governance has to do with the processes by which the institutions attain their corporate objectives. The core objective of the MFIs is to promote national development through greater financial accessibility to the populations that are under served, especially to the poor (Helms, 2006). Equally, as Amha (2008) observes, the majority of MFIs are focused on reducing poverty by targeting its clients who have been traditionally excluded by formal financial institutions.

Governance is important in the microfinance sector in steering institutions towards the attainment of their core goals as well as making them sustainable. Hartarska (2005) observes that the governance mechanisms offer an assurance to the donors, equity investors, and other funds suppliers that their funds are spent in the way that they intended them to be. Bassem (2009) and Hartarska (2005) also indicate that various governance mechanisms have unequal

impacts on outreach and sustainability; some mechanisms have more influence on the outreach, whereas others on financial sustainability. This means that the performance outcomes of the MFIs are greatly influenced by the governance structures.

the weakness in the governance systems, the risk management procedures, internal controls systems and weak regulatory and supervisory systems leads some microfinance institutions in Ethiopia to fail (Mekonen, 2007). For instance, the mistakes of Asser MFI that had the same institutional weaknesses also led to its eventual liquidation (Amha, 2008). Considering these issues, it is necessary to investigate the connection between corporate governance and MFIs performance.

Globally, there are several studies conducted on corporate governance and firm performance (Bassem, 2009; Hartarska, 2005; Kyereboah-Coleman & Osei, 2008; Mohamed et al., 2014; Mersland & Strom, 2009; Vishwakarwa, 2015). However, most of these studies were conducted under circumstances with well-developed governance structures, political stability, and advanced economies. Hence, their findings cannot be generalized to the Ethiopian MFIs. Unlike the type of MFIs in Ethiopia which are not institutions that operate primarily for profits, they use more different ownership strategies. Instead, they are the most part used as a government was done and tools for implementing development programs and strategies to solve socio-economic problems (Amha, 2008).

While some studies attempted to address corporate governance in Ethiopian companies (Amanueal et al., 2015; Freed, 2012; Getachew, 2014; Techan, 2012), they focused on banks and insurance firms rather than microfinance institutions. However, few studies have been done on MFIs in Ethiopia, and they often are limited in terms of sample size or the range of governance variables investigated. For example, Melkamu (2016) only considered five MFIs over a ten-year period leading to a low number of observations. In order to enhance the empirical evidence, the current study increases both the number of observations and sample. Furthermore, Roy Mersland et al. (2018) focused on the influence of board committees per se on MFIs performance in Ethiopia but omitted other vital corporate governance variables, including the regularity of board meetings, directors' competency and financial experience. To the extent of researcher knowledge, there is limited empirical research exists on corporate

governance and the outreach and financial sustainability of MFIs in the Ethiopian context. Thus, this study distinguishes itself from existing literature by exploring the relationship between corporate governance characteristics and microfinance institutions' sustainability and outreach performance in Ethiopia.

There are several contributions of this study to the literature first, it contributes to the scarce empirical literature on corporate governance and performance of microfinance institutions (MFIs) in Ethiopia where previous studies have primarily addressed banking and insurance sectors. Second, the study analyses financial as well as social performance since MFIs have a dual mission. Third, it presents a holistic examination as several corporate governance variables have been included such as board size, gender diversity, frequency of board meetings, financial experience on the board and educational qualification along with audit committee size. Fourth, this study provides more rigorous empirical evidence than existing studies as it employs a larger sample size from previous studies and overcomes certain pitfalls in their observations. Ultimately, the results provide practical significance to MFIs and regulators in designing governance structure balancing reaching out for those who are underserved economically while achieve financial sustainability.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a short description of the corporate governance in Ethiopia. Section 3 presents the existing prior literature on corporate governance and MFIs performance; section 4 describes the data and model specifications. In Section 5, estimation results and discussions are given. Finally, section 6 concludes.

II. Overview of Microfinance Institution in Ethiopia.

The Ethiopian economy was state-manipulated during the imperial government of Haile Selassie in a chain of industrial development plans. Under the Derg rule (1974-91), fiscal institutions were instructed to fund some of the government projects which may not have undergone financial scrutiny (Yesuf, 2010). Following the political transformation in the year 1991, policy reforms were undertaken correspondingly, which included the shift to a free market economy, agrarian-developed economy and the liberalization of the financial sector. Towards that end, issuance of the Proclamation No. 84 /94 was made to permit the involvement of domestic investors who were private in the operations of banks and insurance

operations formerly controlled by government. Therefore, the official microfinance sector in Ethiopia began in 1994/95. The making of this declaration did not however resolve the financial issues of economically active poor people in the rural and urban areas on its own (Seifu, 2002).

Proclamation No. 40/96 was yet another declaration which took place in order to solve the issue of providing the poor with financial services. After the adoption of this proclamation, various NGOs became microfinance institutions, and there are currently 35 MFIs in Ethiopia (National Bank of Ethiopia). The microfinance sector in Ethiopia thus recorded impressive outreaching and sustainability growth. Specifically, the government proclamation facilitated the expansion of microfinance institutions (MFIs), both in the rural and the urban regions, through the Licensing and Supervision of Microfinance Institutions Proclamation which gave the MFIs the right to legally accept deposits by the general population, to attract and accept drafts as well as to operate funds to support the micro-financing services and products (Getaneh, 2005).

III. Empirical evidence on corporate governance and firm performance.

The literature review gives understanding of how different corporate governance mechanisms relate to bank performance based on four factors namely board size, board composition, directors' shareholding, corporate governance disclosure, and audit committee size. Up to this date, various researches have been carried out on the connection between corporate governance and firm performance.

Obi (2016) also discovered that there were positive relations between the shareholding of directors and corporate governance disclosure and the performance of banks, whereas the study by Bebeji et al. (2015) demonstrated the existence of both positive and negative effects of a board size and composition on the return on assets (ROA) and on return on equity (ROE). On the same note, Shaba et al. (2016) have found strong impacts of board composition and gender diversity on market price per share and market capitalization, but no results empirically indicated the impact of board size on performance.

Subsequent research by Handa (2018) and Ogunmakin et al. (2020) built upon the connection of corporate governance mechanisms and bank performance and identified important determinants to include CEO duality, board committees, and gender diversity. In their study, Mandiri et al. (2023) determined the relationship of board size and board meetings with the capital structure and bank performance and identified the significantly positive relationships with the debt-to-equity ratios and ROA. Moreover, Ibrahim et al. (2023) explored the impact of boards of directors' size and managerial ownership on after-tax profit and found both a significant positive and negative effect of these factors, respectively.

Regardless of the wide scope of research done in the field, there are some gaps that should be filled through additional research. To begin with, there are discrepancies in the results of the studies, which implies that better methods should be developed. Second, some of the corporate governance practices including diversity in the board and board size need to be further researched to comprehend their entire effect on the bank performance. Finally, existing studies are mostly related to banks in Nigeria and Indonesia, which implies that the research should be conducted in other geographical areas to determine the extent to which results can be generalized and to evaluate the implication of the governance practices in various settings. This paper, therefore, analyses the impact of corporate governance on the performance of microfinance institutions in Ethiopia.

IV. Material and methods

The study applied explanatory research design with a mixed research method. The data used in the analysis were both primary and secondary. These primary data were gathered by use of administrated questionnaires to the Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) because they can be able to give in detail information on the corporate governance practices in their respective organizations. The questionnaires were to be used to collect the necessary data on corporate governance variables. The audited financial statements of the sampled microfinance institutions were compiled to form the secondary data which were obtained at Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions (AEMFI) and the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE).

1. Model Specification

Following recent empirical studies on corporate governance and firm performance, this study adopts a panel data regression model to examine the relationship between corporate

governance mechanisms and the performance of microfinance institutions (MFIs). Panel data models are widely used in corporate governance research because they allow researchers to capture both cross-sectional differences across firms and changes over time. Recent studies have employed panel regression techniques such as fixed effects and random effects models to analyze the impact of board characteristics and governance structures on organizational performance (Danilov, 2024; Geçici, 2025).

Consistent with these recent studies, the present study specifies a panel data model to examine how corporate governance characteristics influence both the financial performance and social outreach of MFIs.

The general panel data regression model is specified as follows:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1it} + \beta_2 x_{2it} + \dots + \beta_k x_{kit} + \mu_{it} \text{-----}(\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where:

y_{it} represents the dependent variable for institution i at time t ; $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ denotes the microfinance institutions, and $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, T$ represents the time period. β_0 is the constant term, while β_1 to β_k represent the coefficients of the explanatory variables. x_{kit} denotes the independent variables included in the model.

μ_{it} represents the composite error term.

The error term can be decomposed as follows:

$$\mu_{it} = \alpha_i + v_{it} \text{-----}(\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where:

α_i denotes the unobservable individual-specific effect capturing time-invariant characteristics of each MFI, and v_{it} represents the idiosyncratic disturbance term.

Under the random effects model, the individual-specific effect and the disturbance term are assumed to be independently and normally distributed such that:

$$\alpha_i \sim N(0, \sigma_\alpha^2), v_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$$

Based on the above general framework, the empirical model is specified using observable variables to analyse the impact of corporate governance characteristics on the financial and social performance of MFIs.

Model 1: Financial Performance Model

Financial performance is measured by return on assets (ROA), and the model is specified as:

$$roa_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 bsize_{it} + \beta_2 gdiv_{it} + \beta_3 fbm_{it} + \beta_4 bef_{it} + \beta_5 beq_{it} + \beta_6 acsize_{it} + \beta_7 mfisize_{it} + \beta_8 mfiage_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Model 2: Social Performance Model

Social performance is measured by outreach, proxied by the number of credit clients served:

$$outreach_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 bsize_{it} + \beta_2 gdiv_{it} + \beta_3 fbm_{it} + \beta_4 bef_{it} + \beta_5 beq_{it} + \beta_6 acsize_{it} + \beta_7 mfisize_{it} + \beta_8 mfiage_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Were

- roa = return on assets (financial performance)
- outreach = number of credit clients served (social performance)
- bsize = board size
- gdiv = board gender diversity
- fbm = frequency of board meetings
- bef = board members' experience in finance
- beq = educational qualification of the board
- acsize = audit committee size
- mfisize = size of the microfinance institution
- mfiage = age of the microfinance institution
- β_0 = intercept
- β_1 – β_8 = coefficients of explanatory variables
- μ_{it} = error term

Table 1 Definition and Measurements of independent, and control variables

Independent Variable	Definition	Measurement	Reference
Board size (BSIZE)	Board size defined as a number of directors on board	Total number of members	Hartarska (2005); Mersland & Strøm (2009)
Gender diversity (GDIV)	Board Gender represent number of women on the board	Total female board divided by total number of board members	Adams & Ferreira (2009); Mersland & Strøm (2009)

Frequency of board meeting (FBM)	Frequency of board meeting means the number of meetings conducted by the board in a particular year	The frequency of board meetings in a given year	Vafeas (1999); Mersland & Strøm (2009)
Board educational qualification (BEQ)	The educational background of MFI board members	The proportion of board members who have a college degree and above	Anderson et al. (2011); Mersland & Strøm (2009)
Audit committee size (ACSIZE)	Audit Committee Members of MFIs on Boards of Directors	Number of members of audit committee over the total board size	Bebeji et al. (2015); DeZoort et al. (2002)
Board member experience in finance (BEF)	A board member with finance and related work experience	The proportion of board members with finance experience	Mersland & Strøm (2009); Handa (2018)
MFI SIZE	It is the size of the microfinance institution	The logarithm of the year-end total assets	Cull et al. (2007); Hermes & Lensink (2011)
MFI AGE	The age of MFI from the time when it is established	Number of years from their commencement	Cull et al. (2007); Mersland & Strøm (2009)

V. Econometric Evidence and Discussion

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs.	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Return on asset	90	-.322	2.776	0.156	.406
Number of Clients	90	5.236	14.210	9.467	2.503
Board SIZE	90	4	9	6.311	1.186
Gender diversity	90	0	1	0.288	0.230

Frequency	90	2	13	5.889	2.869
Board meeting					
Board	90	1	7	3.278	1.499
Experience					
Board	90	.5	1	.924	.118
Educational					
qualification					
Audit	90	0	4	1.767	1.289
Committee size					
AGE of MFI	90	1	24	13	5.559
SIZE OF MFI	90	6.438	17.113	11.999	2.514

Source: Stata descriptive statistics result based on the data obtained from sample MFI, 2020

Table 3 indicates that the microfinance institutions (MFIs) had a mean of 0.156 on the return on assets (ROA) with a minimum of -0.322 and maximum of 2.776. It means that MFIs earned an average of 15.6 percent on each 1 birr they invested in assets.

Ethiopian MFIs had an average number of 6 board members. This falls short of the minimum board size of 7 members by the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE). Nonetheless, the largest size of the board was 9, whereas there was also 4 as a minimum. It implies that Ethiopian MFIs do not necessarily comply with the recommended board size but some of the institution have boards with nine members which exceed the recommended size.

The latter is also low according to Table 3, with only 28.78% of the board members being female with a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 1 (100%). It means that the male membership dominates in MFI boards. The findings also show that there are a few MFIs which have no female members in their boards as a disheartening outcome of gender inclusiveness.

The mean experience of directors in the finance related experience was 3 with a minimum of 1 and a maximum of 7 members of the board. This exceeds the requirement by the National Bank of Ethiopia. Moreover, the number of meetings that the board of directors' conducts is on average about 6 time per year with a minimum of 2 and maximum of 13 meetings with a standard deviation of 2.869. The National Bank of Ethiopia however needs board meetings to be conducted once every month and this is equivalent to twelve meetings in a year. However, most MFIs conduct board meetings that are not in this requirement.

The size of the audit committee of Ethiopian MFIs is approximately 2 members with a minimum of 0 members and a maximum of 4 members. This means that even though certain MFIs have audit committees in charge of the financial reporting matters, there are those which do not have an audit committee. Lastly, the mean age of MFIs is 13 years with the least age of 1 year and the highest age of 24 years. This indicates that the number of years that Ethiopian MFIs have been in operation differs significantly.

VI Random effect GLS regressions

Table 9 presents the report of random effects panel data estimates on the interconnection between corporate governance, and financial and social performance results of MFIs. Model one in table 8 shows the result for financial performance by using ROA as a proxy. On the contrary, model two demonstrate results for social performance (outreach) in which NCC employed as a proxy.

Table 1 results for Model 1 (ROA) and model 2 (NCC)

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	ROA		NCC	
	Cof.	Std. Err.	Cof.	Std. Err.
bsiz	0.245***	0.048	-0.476**	0.239
gdiv	0.128	0.277	6.059***	1.432
fbm	-0.011	0.011	0.291***	0.054
bef	0.103***	0.036	-0.502***	0.181
eqb	1.600***	0.326	-0.302	1.602
acsiz	0.011	0.026	-0.180	0.125
mfsiz	-0.023	0.036	0.150	0.191
mfiage	-0.003	0.014	-0.116	0.074
cons	-2.882	0.498	10.963	2.562
Wald chi2(8) = 65.11		Wald chi2(8) = 54.53		
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000		Prob > chi2 = 0.0000		
rho = 81.4%		rho = 87.4%		
R square; within = 0.6003		R square; within = 0.5279		
Between=0.0183		Between= 0.0112		
Over all= 0.0671		Over all= 0.0022		
N.B *significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, *** significant at 1%				

Source: Stata 14 regression results based on data obtained from sample MFIs.

The outcome of the random-effects GLS regression indicates that the R-squared of the model is 60.03% and 52.79% as per the two models respectively. It implies that about 60.03 percent of the changes in ROA and 52.79 percent of the changes in NCC can be explained by the explanatory variables in the models. The other 39.97 and 47.21 percentage of variation of ROA and NCC respectively is attributed to other factors which are not considered in the models. The Wald chi-square statistics of the two models of 65.11 and 54.53 have a p-value of 0.0000 which is statistically significant, thus showing that the coefficients of the two models are not simultaneously equal to zero. This implies that the independent variables jointly identify the variation in the dependent variables. Also, the values of rho (ρ) between the two models show that the variance associated with the differences between the panel units is about 81.4% and 87.4%. This suggests that a high level of the total variance is because differences between cross section of the institutions contained in the panel dataset

This research explored impact of corporate governance characteristics on financial and social performance of microfinance institutions (MFI). Financial performance was measured by return on assets (ROA) and social performance by outreach, or number of credit clients served. The findings indicate that board size positively and statistically significantly impacts financial performance at the 1% level of significance. In other words, hypothesizing that all the circumstances keep unchanging, each additional member in board increases ROA by 24.5%. This indicates that the long-term financial well-being of MFIs improves in cases where MFIs have bigger boards. One possible explanation is that boards with more people have a greater variety of skills, backgrounds, and expertise, which can assist with strategic decision-making and strengthen management oversight. It supports the works of Sonia Bassem (2009) and Roy Mersland and R. Oystein Strom (2009), both showing that board characteristics are important to improve MFIs sustainability. However, this result is at odds with Michael C. Jensen's (1993) argument that larger boards can negatively affect efficiency due to difficulties in coordination as well as communication issues.

Board size has negative and statistically significant effect on outreach with respect to social performance at the 5% level of significance. The study finds that adding one more board member is associated with MFIs serving 47.6% fewer credit clients, other things being equal.

This also makes it so boards with more members may not be able to get in touch with as many people. This might well be attributable to the regulatory framework that governs banks and other financial institutions established by the National Bank of Ethiopia. These rules force them to comply with certain regulations and closely monitor their financials. This kind of regulatory pressure may lead board members to put finances before their social goal of helping low-income consumers. This finding conforms to prior work suggesting that larger boards prioritize financial objectives over social outreach.

The paper also examined how the performance of MFIs relates to a mixed board of women and men. The result indicates that the presence of women on the board does not have a statistically significant effect on financial performance, so gender diversity does not significantly affect ROA. However, gender diversity has a positive and statistically significant impact on social performance (outreach) at the 1% significance level. A one percentage point increase in women on the board results in a 60.59% increase in MFIs credit clients served. The implication is that, there are significant value addition in having women on board when it comes to communicating with low-income clients. This may be because women trust that they better understand what low-income clients want and may assist MFIs in making products more appropriate for these groups of people. These findings undermine Roy Mersland and R. Oystein Strom (2007) by suggesting that boards with women could help boards connect with poor clients. In common with most world organizations, women in management can increase their institutions productivity since they make a good order of decisions and multitasking (Mehmet Kilic, 2015). That finding is consistent with past empirical research indicating the importance of gender diversity among a microfinance institution's membership in pursuing its social objectives.

The findings also indicate that the frequency of board meetings does not have a statistically significant impact on the financial performance of the company. However, we find that while the number of board meetings has a positive and statistically significant influence on social performance (outreach) at 1% level of significance. When board members meet more frequently and others are constant, the number of credit clients increases by 29.1%. In other words, more frequently meeting boards are more engaged in monitoring and guiding management. This then helps MFIs achieve their social goals. This finding aligns with the

reason of agency theory that more frequent board meetings enhance monitoring systems and help organizations perform better through better surveillance of how well managers carry out their duties.

The study also investigated the impact of financial experience among board members on MFI performance. Board members with financial experience positively and statistically significantly influence the financial performance up to 1% level of significance per our results. And the findings indicate that ROA increases by 10.3% for every additional financial expert on the board (holding everything else constant). It proves that finance-savvy directors serve as a good steward of the company by providing knowledge and expertise on financial management and strategic planning to preserve its stability. These results are aligned with what Freed (2012) and Melkamu (2016) found in their studies, where both concluded that there was a favorable correlation between board financial expertise and financial performance. However, financially experienced board members have a negative and statistically significant effect on social performance (outreach) at the 1% level of significance. One financial literate board member reduces the number of credit clients by 50.2% according to the results. This would mean that boards predominantly comprised of money-centric individuals might prioritize financial sustainability over committing to social engagement. The National Bank of Ethiopia may promote knowledgeable board members on money matters to enhance compliance with its rules. This may understandably lead to board members being more concerned with ensuring that the company is financially sound and compliant than about going out of their way for clients who are less fortunate. This finding is in line with the observation made by Anita Hartarska (2005) on trade-off between financial sustainability and social mission of micro finance institutions.

They also indicate that the board's level of education has a positive and statistically significant relationship with financial performance at 1% significance level. The results indicate that a more educated board does significantly influence ROA (the only measure of performance), though it is the flipped picture. This can be critical in order for MFIs to remain financially sustainable, so this means more educated directors can provide this crucial knowledge, analytical skills and strategic advice. This discovery supports resource dependency theory which posits that board members with extensive experience and

knowledge act as resources by facilitating access to external information and improving strategic decision-making. This result supports previous studies conducted by Anita Hartarska (2005), Ferde (2012) and Qaiser Yasser (2011) who argue that the competent levels of highly educated directors are superior when assessing management decisions, challenging corporate processes and reducing agency problems.

On the contrary, there was a negative but not statistically significant correlation between social performance and education level of board. Thus, having highly educated board members is an implication of financial procyclicality among MFIs, whereas the impact on the number of low-income clients served is negligible. Lastly, the findings reveal that the size of audit committee does not have any statistically significant effect on financial or social performance of MFIs. Governance frameworks such as audit committees are meant to promote transparency and accountability, but this study shows that the size of an audit committee, alone, does not significantly affect MFIs' financial stability or outreach performance.

VII. Conclusions

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) are organizations that provide financial services to low-income individuals and communities. Corporate governance refers to the systems, processes, and principles by which an organization is directed and controlled. In the microfinance sector, effective corporate governance is crucial because donors, investors, and other funding providers need assurances that the funds provided will be used effectively and in alignment with the mission of MFIs. This study explores the relationship between corporate governance and performance, in terms of outreach and sustainability among MFIs. The empirical analysis was conducted based on primary data obtained from individual microfinance institutions, as well as secondary data collected from the National Bank of Ethiopia and the association of Ethiopian microfinance institutions (AEMFI). From random effect regression model, results indicate the higher for improvement in financial performance as board size, educational qualification and board experience.

This analysis specifically considered the important characteristics of board, such as board size, gender diversity in boards (members), number of meetings held by a board members, attending financial experience index for board members, educational attainment or qualification of the board servants and audit committee size. Return on assets (ROA) was used to measure financial performance and outreach, as the number of credit clients served, was used as a proxy for social performance. The study is based on the theory of agency and resource dependency theory that governs how governance influence organizational results.

The empirical results demonstrate different effects of the corporate governance mechanisms on MFIs finance and social performance. The findings demonstrate that board size has a positive and statistically significant impact on the financial performance, which means that larger boards are associated with better financial sustainability. This may result from the presence of board members with a broad background, skills, and experience that contribute to strategic decision-making and oversight. On the other hand, board size had an adverse, significant effect on social performance and may indicate that larger boards favor financial goals over outreach to poorer clientele.

The results also suggest that it does not have a strong influence on financial performance coming from gender diversity of the board. On the contrary, it has a positive and statistically significant impact on social performance. This reflects the fact that having women on boards appears to facilitate outreach and broadens access to financial services for clients with fewer resources. Women on corporate boards may have a better understanding of the needs of underserved populations and foster developments of financial products that fill those needs. The frequency of board meeting was not found statistically significant on financial performance but positive and statistically significant effect on social outreach. This means that boards holding more regular meetings are likely to monitor and guide management better, making the institution more committed to its social mission.

Our further analysis shows that companies are benefitting from the financial experience of board members when it comes to financial performance, but this financial background has a negative impact on social performance. The appointment of financially savvy directors strengthens the financial stewardship which can lead to more effective long-term financial sustainable strategies. However, their attention to financial results might serve to diminish

the social goal of serving poorer clients. In the same way, board educational qualification has a positive and significant effect on financial performance. The relationship between board educational qualification and social performance was negative but statistically insignificant, indicating that the theory of change deriving from improved outreach to poorer clients through educational competency is by no means a given.

Finally, the results indicate that audit committee size is not statistically significantly associated with financial or social performance. This implies that the presence of an audit committee does not necessarily correlate to better operational performance for MFIs.

VII RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results and conclusions above, the researcher provided the following recommendations to MFIs and NBE.

First, MFIs should aim to strike the right board size by balancing desired expertise with efficiency (large boards can be less effective). The study found that while larger boards improve financial performance, they can affect negatively social outreach. Thus, while it is important for boards to have diverse skills and experience, they also should be effective at making decisions and coordinating.

Second, MFIs and regulators could combat gender inequality by advocating for diversity on boards. Our results show that boards with women also have far better social outreach, measured through the number of credit clients served. It implies that female directors help better articulate poor customers' needs and may aid in designing services/products which are inclusive. Hence MFIs must promote appointment of suitable women into board level positions.

Third, MFIs must make sure that boards convene regularly and engage with governance activities. The findings suggest that frequent board meetings facilitate outreach, which positively affect firm's social performance. Regular meetings give board members a greater opportunity to oversee management activity, convey strategic direction, and encourage commitment to the institution's social mission.

Fourth, even if the financial skills of board members are more crucial for enhancing the finance sustainability of MFIs, including board members with social development experience

is also essential. The study questioned whether board members with financial acumen prioritize the cost benefit of financial performance ahead of social outreach. As a result, an appropriate mix of members with financial and non-financial backgrounds may assist MFIs in realizing their twin goals of sustainability and outreach.

Fifth, MFIs need to keep the trend of hiring well-educated and capable board members as results indicate that the educational qualification of board mandatorily enhances financial performance. Informed board members are more effective in their review of strategic matters, judgement about management decisions, and assistance to the sustainability of the institution. Sixth, despite audit committee size not found influencing performance significantly, MFIs should still ensure that their audit committees functioned effectively. It is the quality, independence and expertise of audit committee members that matters rather than size just for sizes sake. Last, but not least, regulators and policy makers – above all the central bank and relevant financial authorities – should prepare governance guidelines that weigh financial sustainability against the social mission of MFIs. Whilst regulatory frameworks tend to focus on financial stability, encouraging appropriate governance structures can also facilitate outreach to poorer and underserved populations.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, T.Y.W Methodology, T.Y.W, AND J.R.; resources T.Y.W.. And J.R.; data duration, T.Y.W. writing- original draft preparation, J.R., Writing- review and editing, we have read and agreed to the publication version of the manuscript.

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Competing Interest

There is no conflicting interest in this manuscript.

➤ Data Availability Statement

Data are available upon request.

8. Reference

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